

CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS AS PRODUCTS OF PEOPLE'S COGNITION

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Abstract

Metaphors are products of people's cognition and they are inevitable part of our everyday life and conversation. For several years, until 1980 - CMT - Conceptual Metaphor Theory was worked out by Lakoff and Johnson metaphors used to be treated as an unusual embellishment used only in literature or/and poetry. However, in *Metaphors We Live By* (1980) Lakoff and Johnson proved the contradictory. Metaphors are used by people on a daily basis without even noticing that they are actually speaking with metaphors. In this article we can observe several examples of conceptual metaphors used in different contexts.

Key words: conceptual metaphors, cognitive metaphors, source domain, target domain, metaphorical projection, the frame, the focus, conceptual metaphor theory, ontological metaphors, orientational metaphors.

Lakoff and Johnson have a progressive understanding about how metaphors can change over time. New metaphors are creative and imaginative and can change the very way we think: *Love is a collaborative work of art, Love is work, Love is active, Love requires cooperation, Love requires dedication, Love requires patience, Love brings frustration, Love needs communication, Love is aesthetic, Love involves creativity, Love requires a shared aesthetic, Love cannot be achieved by formula.*¹

Again the above mentioned metaphors demonstrate how they have become an essential and inseparable part of our lives.

Carolla Scott looks at metaphors about cancer and argues that this can help us understand how we can gain richer understanding of how we structure abstract emotional or other experiences that are not clearly delineated: *Cancer is another eating and invading the body, combatting cancer.*²

For the study of Cognitive Linguistics conceptual or cognitive metaphors serve as the basic type of metaphor for research. Lakoff and Johnson are firm advocators of cognitive study of metaphor and their work *Metaphors We Live By* has marked the establishment of the cognitive approach to metaphor. They think

¹ Lakoff and Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By*, 1980: 24

² Scott *Expressive Metaphors in Cancer Narratives*, 2002: 230-235.

that metaphor is omnipresent and a prevalent phenomenon in ordinary language. Our conceptual system is largely metaphorical, and our ordinary conceptual system, in terms of which we both think and act, is fundamentally metaphorical in nature.³ They have made a penetrating systematic analysis of metaphorical concept system which exists in our thought system and made a distinction between conceptual metaphors and linguistic metaphors (or metaphoric expressions). As the basis for their study they highlighted *conceptual metaphors*.

Conceptual metaphors typically employ a more abstract concept as target and a more concrete or physical concept as their source. For instance, metaphors such as 'the days ahead' or 'giving my time' rely on more concrete concepts, thus expressing time as a path into physical space, or as a substance that can be handled and offered as a gift. Different conceptual metaphors tend to be invoked when the speaker is trying to make a case for a certain point of view or course of action. For instance, one might associate "the days ahead" with leadership, whereas the phrase "giving my time" carries stronger connotations of bargaining. Selection of such metaphors tends to be directed by a subconscious or implicit purpose, in the mind of the person employing them.

Conceptual or cognitive metaphors include familiar comparisons that do not attract attention as a figure of speech. A conceptual metaphor is heard or read in everyday language in a certain culture, and it lends some credibility to that specific culture's understanding of the statement. A conceptual domain can be any mental organization of human experience. The regularity with which different languages employ the same metaphors, often perceptually based, has led to the hypothesis that the mapping between conceptual domains corresponds to neural mappings in the brain. Graph 1 below shows the correspondence between the domains of metaphor

Graph 1.2. The correspondence between source and target domains

³ Lakoff & Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By*, 1980 3.

Examples of conceptual metaphors include:

- Time is running out.
- Time flies.
- It is time to move forward with your life.
- You're wasting my time.
- I have to finish this article and it is a race against time.
- Spend your time in a smart fashion.

The linguists of the English language, have differed much difference in determining the elements of metaphor. For Max Black, metaphor is not one word, but it is the entire sentence. It is composed of two pillars: a) the frame: the context in which it was received by the metaphor; and b) the focus: the word used metaphorically.

Richards makes three pillars of metaphor.⁴ The first pillar is the tenor. It is the element that is described by the metaphor. The second pillar is the vehicle, which is the borrowed word. The third pillar is the ground. It is the similarity ground between the described element and the vehicle of similarity.

Newmark, who is one of the most prolific theorists of translation production in terms of his circulation and investigation of metaphor, says that metaphor has four pillars. The object is the first of these pillars, that is the element which describes metaphor. Second, the image, that is the element which described by the object. Third, the sense, that is what shows the similarities between the object and the image. Fourth, the metaphor, a word or words taken from the image.⁵

Conceptual metaphors are useful for understanding complex ideas in simple terms and therefore are frequently used to give insight to abstract

⁴ Newmark, A Textbook of Translation, 1988: 70.

⁵ *ibid*: 75.

theories and models. So not only is our everyday communication shaped by the language of conceptual metaphors, but so is the very way we understand scholarly theories. These metaphors are prevalent in communication and we do not just use them in language; we actually perceive and act in accordance with the metaphors.

Conceptual Metaphor Theory

In Conceptual Metaphor Theory, metaphor is not "a decorative device, peripheral to language and thought". The theory holds instead that conceptual metaphors are "central to thought, and therefore to language".⁶ From this theory, a number of basic tenets are derived:

- ✓ Metaphors structure thinking;
- ✓ Metaphors structure knowledge;
- ✓ Metaphor is central to abstract language;
- ✓ Metaphor is grounded in physical experience;
- ✓ Metaphor is ideological.

Conceptual metaphors can be of three kinds: structural, ontological, orientational.⁷ In the structural metaphors the source domain provides a relatively rich knowledge structure for the target concept.

In other words, the cognitive function of these metaphors is to enable speakers to understand target A by means of the structure of source B. This understanding takes place by means of conceptual mappings between elements of A and elements of B. The examples given so far are structural metaphors:

- **Time is money.**
 - You're *running out of time*.
 - *Put aside some time for* ping-pong.
 - Do you *have some time left*?
 - He's living on *borrowed time*.
 - *Thank you for your time*.

The following features of conceptual metaphors can be defined:

1) metaphors serve as a transition from familiar to unknown, therefore, source domains compared to target domains are usually more precise, understandable through the direct experience and are easier to use in communication;

⁶ Lakoff, Turner, More Than Cool Reason, 1989: 55.

⁷ Lakoff & Johnson, Metaphors We Live By, 1980: 14.

2) spheres connected with metaphors are asymmetrical and unequal: the metaphor LOVE IS A JOURNEY exists, but there is no opposite metaphor JOURNEY IS LOVE as physical events are not conceived through abstract notions;

3) as a rule, metaphors emphasize certain aspects of comparison, e.g. the metaphor TIME IS MONEY highlights the function of money but not on a size of a note;

4) metaphors function at different levels of certainty, some at a higher, more general one, others at a more specific level; metaphors of a higher level have a more universal character which allows them to appear in different languages and cultures whereas metaphors of a lower level are rather culturally presupposed.⁸

Ontological metaphors provide much less cognitive structuring for target concepts than structural ones do. Their cognitive job seems to be to give an ontological status to general categories of abstract target concepts. That means that we conceive of our experiences in terms of objects, substances, and containers, in general, without specifying exactly what kind of object, substance, and container is meant. In general, ontological metaphors enable us to see more sharply delineated structure where there is very little or none.

Container metaphors help us think about how we relate to a concept, whether we're part of it, in it, experiencing it or not, but all of these metaphors can be mixed together, they're not mutually exclusive. To illustrate, the metaphor *Love is a journey* can bring about other metaphors such as *Look how far we've come*, *We're at a crossroads*, *We'll just have to go our separate ways*, *We can't turn back now*, *I don't think this relationship is going anywhere*, *Where are we?* *We're stuck*, *It's been a long bumpy road*, *This relationship is a dead-end street*, *Our marriage is on the rocks*. *We've gotten off the track*, *This relationship is foundering*.

Given that undelineated experiences receive a more delineated status via ontological metaphors, speakers can use these metaphors for more specific jobs:

1) to refer, to quantify, to identify aspects of the experience that has been made more delineated. For example, conceiving of fear as an object, we can conceptualise it as *our possession*. Thus, we can linguistically refer to fear as *my fear*, or *your fear*. Cases like this are the least noticeable types of conceptual metaphors.

⁸ Lakoff & Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By*, 1980: 27.

2) Once a *nothing* has received a status of a thing through an ontological metaphor, the experience so conceptualised can be structured further by means of structural metaphors.

- **The mind is a machine.**

- We're still trying to *grind out the solution to this equation*.
- My mind isn't just *operating* today.
- Boy, the *wheels are turning* now.
- I'm *a little rusty* today.
- We've been working on this problem all day and now we're *running*

out of steam.

- **States are containers.**

- She's *in love*.
- We're *in trouble* now.
- He's *coming out of the coma*.
- I'm slowly *getting into shape*.
- He *entered a state of euphoria*.
- He *fell into a depression*.

Personification is a case of widening of ontological metaphor each of which is based on a specific feature of a human or on the way it is perceived "in terms of own motivations, goals, actions and qualities".⁹

Oriental metaphors provide even less conceptual structure for target concepts than ontological ones. Their cognitive job, instead, is to make a set of target concepts coherent in our conceptual system. The name derives from the fact that most metaphors that serve this function have to do with basic human spatial orientations, such as up-down, center-periphery, etc. According to Lakoff and Johnson's view: "Since there are systematic correlates between our emotions (like happiness) and our sensory-motor experiences (like erect posture), these form the basis of orientational metaphorical concepts (such as happy is up). Such metaphors allow us to conceptualize our emotions in more sharply define terms and also to relate them to other concepts having to do with general well-being (e.g. health, life, control, etc)".¹⁰

- **Happy is up; sad is down.**

- I'm *feeling up*.
- That *boosted my spirits*.
- You're in *high spirits*.

⁹ Lakoff & Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By*, 1980: 29.

¹⁰ Lakoff & Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By*, 1980: 32.

- Thinking about her always *gives me a lift*.
- I'm *depressed*.
- He's really *low* these days.
- I *fell* into a depression.

Experiential basis for such a metaphorization is the position of a human body, i.e. when a human feels depressed or sad his body is bent whereas upright position signifies positive emotional state.

- **Conscious is up; unconscious is down.**
 - Get *up*.
 - I'm *up* already.
 - He *rises* early in the morning.
 - He *fell* asleep.
 - He's *under* hypnosis.
 - He *sank* into a coma.
- **Health and life are up; sickness and death are down.**
 - He's at the *peak* of health.
 - Lazarus *rose* from death.
 - He *fell* ill.
 - He came *down* with the flu.
 - He *dropped* dead.
- **More is up; less is down.**
 - The number of books printed each year keeps *going up*.
 - His draft number is *high*.
 - My income *rose* last year.
 - The number of errors he made is incredibly *low*.
 - He is *underage*.
 - His income *fell* last year.

Such spatial relations occur due to the existence of the very human body which is involved in the interaction with the outside world. That is why the "up-down" orientation is grounded on the fact that when a baby grows up and develops it moves upwards and when learning to walk it tries to take a vertical position.¹¹

In summary, metaphors are products of people's cognition and they are inevitable part of our everyday life and conversation. For several years, until 1980 - CMT - Conceptual Metaphor Theory was worked out by Lakoff and Johnson metaphors used to be treated as an unusual embellishment used only in

¹¹ Kartashova, Cognitive Metaphor in Modern Linguistics, 2008: 4-9.

literature or/and poetry. However, in *Metaphors We Live By* (1980) Lakoff and Johnson proved the contradictory. Metaphors are used by people on a daily basis without even noticing that they are actually speaking with metaphors. This again shows that metaphors are a product of people cognition and worldview.

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